

23. F. D. GUNSTONE, J. A. HOLLIDAY and C. M. SCRIMGEOUR, *Chem. Phys. Lypads* 1977, 20, 331.
 24. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier, New York, 1957, p. 127.
 25. E. STAHL, "Thin-Layer Chromatography", 2nd. ed., Toppan, Tokyo, 1969, p. 737.
 26. D. T. PLUMMER, "An Introduction to Practical Biochemistry", 2nd ed., Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 1979, pp 83, 144.
 27. D. ABBOTT and R. S. ANDREWS, "An Introduction to Chromatography", Houghton Mifflin, Boston, 1965, p. 18.
 28. D. J. BHATT, A. J. BAXI and A. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 98.

Specific Separation of Chromium(III) from Mixture with numerous Metal Ions by Tlc on Silica Gel-G Layers in HCl and DMSO-HCl systems

S. D. SHARMA* and B. M. SETHI

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College Moradabad-244 001

Manuscript received 16 April 1985, revised 12 August 1986, accepted 5 September 1986

SILICA gel-G has been used extensively for the separation of organic and inorganic substances¹.

A number of non-aqueous systems have been used as eluants. A search of the literature reveals that no work has been reported on the specific separation of Cr^{III} from mixture with numerous metal ions on silica gel-G layers. The present work was therefore undertaken and a number of interesting separations achieved in pure DMSO and DMSO-HCl systems.

Experimental

A Toshniwal tlc apparatus for the preparation of silica gel-G layers on 20×3 cm glass plates was used. The plates were developed in glass jars (20×6 cm).

Silica gel-G (B.D.H., England) and DMSO (B.D.H., England) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Solutions (0.1 M) of chlorides, nitrates or sulphates of most of the cations were prepared in 0.1 M solutions of the corresponding acids. The solutions of sodium molybdate, sodium tungstate, sodium selenite and sodium tellurite were prepared in water. The solutions of Nb^V and Ta^V were prepared as reported earlier². Conventional spot-test reagents were used for detection purposes³.

Procedure: Silica gel-G plates (~0.15 mm thick) were prepared as usual. The cation solutions were spotted on the plates with thin glass capillaries. After drying the spots, plates were developed in the chosen solvent system by the ascending technique. The solvent was allowed to ascend 11 cm from the

starting line on the plate in all cases. *R_f* values were then measured as usual.

Solvent systems: The solvent systems used were: (i) 1 M HCl, (ii) DMSO, (iii) DMSO-1 M HCl (1 : 1), (iv) DMSO-1 M HCl (9 : 1), (v) DMSO-2 M HCl (1 : 1), (vi) DMSO-4 M HCl (1 : 9), (vii) DMSO-4 M HCl (1 : 1), (viii) DMSO-6 M HCl (1 : 9), (ix) DMSO-6 M HCl (3 : 7), (x) DMSO-6 M HCl (1 : 1), and (xi) DMSO-6 M HCl (9 : 1).

Systems studied: (i) Binary mixtures: Cr^{III} from Ag^I or Hg₂^{II} or Sn^{II} or Sn^{IV} or ZrO^{II} in 1 M HCl; Cr^{III} from Hg^{II} or Pd^{II} or VO^{II} or Pt^{IV} in pure DMSO; and Cr^{III} from Ag^I or Pb^{II} or Sb^{III} or Sn^{II} or Sn^{IV} or Y^{III} or ZrO^{II} or Th^{IV} or Ti^{IV} or In^{III} or Sm^{III} or Hg₂^{II} or K or Mn^{II} or Tl^I or Ba^{II} or Sr^{II} or WO₄²⁻ or TeO₄²⁻ or SeO₄²⁻ in DMSO-HCl systems in varying ratios. (ii) Ternary mixtures: Cr^{III}-Pb^{II}-Y^{III} or Ti^{IV} or TeO₄²⁻ or SeO₄²⁻ or Pt^{IV} in DMSO-1 M HCl (9 : 1); Cr^{III}-Ti^{IV}-Hg₂^{II} or Sn^{IV} or WO₄²⁻ or Nb^V or Ta^V in DMSO-4 M HCl (1 : 9); Cr^{III}-TeO₄²⁻-K or ZrO^{II} or WO₄²⁻ or Ba^{II} in DMSO-4 M HCl (9 : 1); Cr^{III}-MoO₄²⁻-WO₄²⁻ or Sn^{IV} or Mg^{II} or Nb^V in DMSO-4 M HCl (3 : 7); and Cr^{III}-ZrO^{II}-WO₄²⁻ or Ag^I or Nb^V in DMSO-6 M HCl (3 : 7).

Results and Discussion

The separations achieved are predictable and reproducible. This is a direct result of certain unique properties of DMSO, i.e. its high dielectric constant ($\epsilon=47.5$), its ability to solvate metal ions in preference to anions, and a specific solvating effect DMSO favours the formation of chloro complexes in an HCl medium⁴. The advantage of this work lies in the fact that we have been able to separate Cr^{III} ion from the mixtures containing larger amounts of other metal ions such as Ag^I, Hg₂^{II}, Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, ZrO^{II}, Pd^{II}, VO^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III}, Y^{III}, Th^{IV}, Ti^{IV}, In^{III}, Sm^{III}, K, Mn^{II}, Tl^I, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, TeO₄²⁻, SeO₄²⁻ and WO₄²⁻. Out of these, the separation of Cr^{III} from Pb^{II}, Mn^{II}, VO^{II} and WO₄²⁻ is important in alloy analysis. In order to establish the utility of these separations, the synthetic alloy samples of Cr^{III} with Pb^{II}, Mn^{II}, VO^{II} and WO₄²⁻ were prepared by mixing various metallic solutions in certain ratios so that they correspond to the actual metallic proportions in the standard alloys, and then these samples were tried on silica gel-G plates and the metal ion separations were achieved.

The most interesting feature of the study is the increase in the *R_f* value of Cr^{III} from almost zero to nearly one by the addition of HCl to pure DMSO. This can be explained in terms of formation of chloro-complexes of the metal ion which are solvated by DMSO causing a higher *R_f* value. For most of the cations studied, there is no change in *R_f* values with the change in DMSO concentration. The high but constant *R_f* values for most of the ions are due to solvation of the cations or their chloro-complexes.

* Present address : A-83 Gandhi Nagar, Moradabad-244 001.

References

1. U. A. TH. BRINKMAN, G. DE VRIES and R. KURODA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1973, **85**, 187.
2. M. QURESHI and S. D. SHARMA *Chromatographia*, 1978, **11**, 153.
3. M. QURESHI and S. D. SHARMA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **45**, 1283.
4. G. E. JANAUER, H. E. VAN WART and J. T. CARRANO, *Anal. Chem.*, 1970, **42**, 215.

Rapid Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt(II) with Isonitrosothiocamphor

G. S. KATIYAR* and B. C. HALDAR

Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory,
The Institute of Science, Bombay-400 032

Manuscript received 16 August 1985, revised 28 August 1986,
accepted 5 September 1986

ISONITROSOTHIOCAMPHOR (HINTC) reacts with transition metal ions giving coloured complexes which are extractable into organic solvents^{1,2}. The present paper reports a study of the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II} with HINTC.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Radioactivity and pH were measured as described in an earlier communication³.

Reagents and chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Standard solutions of cobalt were prepared by the standard method. Solutions for interference study were obtained by dissolving appropriate salts in water to give 10 mg of element per ml and standardised by the standard method. HINTC was synthesised by the literature method. Radioisotopes was supplied by Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay.

Procedure for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt: For spectrophotometric determination, 2 M NH₄Cl (2 ml) and 0.035% HINTC (1 ml) in alcohol was added to a solution (≈4 ml) containing 1–90 μg of cobalt. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7 with dilute solutions of HCl and/or NH₄OH, and after making the volume 10 ml, it was equilibrated for 1 min with chloroform (10 ml). The organic extract was collected in a 10 ml flask and made upto the mark with chloroform, if necessary. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of cobalt(II) was determined from a calibration curve.

Extraction coefficients of cobalt(II) were determined by using ⁶⁰Co tracer.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of cobalt is greater than 99.5% in the pH range 6.5–7.5 when HINTC and metal are in the molar ratio of 10 : 1 or more and equilibration time is 1 min.

The distribution coefficient (*E*) of cobalt in different solvents were: chloroform (520), benzene (511), methyl isobutyl ketone (504), carbon tetrachloride (160), methyl ethyl ketone (137), toluene (126), nitrobenzene (121) and chlorobenzene (118).

The absorption spectrum of Co–HINTC in chloroform exhibits a shoulder at 520 nm. However, measurements for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt have been taken at 400 nm because absorbance at this wavelength is more than that at 520 nm and absorbance due to the reagent blank is 0.02. The absorbance of the extract remains constant for more than 2 days. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.1–9.0 μg of Co^{II} per ml. Molar extinction coefficient at this wavelength is 7 270 dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Following ions and masking agents when present in amount indicated do not interfere in the spectrophotometric determination of 50 μg of cobalt(II): 10 mg of each of Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, As^{III}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, W^{VI} and Mo^{VI}; 1 mg of each of Sb^{III} and Rb^I; 0.1 mg of each of Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, V^V, Se^{IV}, Ru^{III}, Pt^{IV} and Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, Al^{III}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} were kept in solution by adding tartrate. In the presence of 100 mg of thiosulphate, 0.1 mg of each of Au^{III} and Ag^I, do not interfere. Interference by Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} can be masked by oxalate and thiourea, respectively. 100 mg of each of chloride, bromide, iodide, fluoride, nitrate, tartrate, sulphate, peroxysulphate, thiocyanate, thiourea, urea, thiosulphate, chlorate, bromate and iodate; 50 mg of sulphite; 10 mg of each of oxalate, acetate and phosphate; and 1 mg of citrate and pyrophosphate do not interfere. EDTA and cyanide interfere by hindering the extraction of cobalt.

Nature of the extracted species: Curves obtained by the mole-ratio method and by Job's continuous variation method show a break at the point corresponding to HINTC–Co ratio equal to 3 : 1 indicating that the extracted species is formed by the reaction of cobalt and HINTC in the ratio of 1 : 3.

Precision, accuracy and sensitivity: The average of 10 determinations with 50 μg of cobalt in 10 ml solution is 50.2 μg and it varies between 49.1 and 51.4 μg at 95% confidence limit.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (G.S.K.).